

SKILLS AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF CONSECUTIVE INTERPRETERS

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Annotation. This article is devoted the specific features of consecutive translation. Consecutive interpreting is a type of interpreting in which the interpreter begins to interpret after the speaker has finished all or some part of his speech. That is, the translator does not translate in parallel with the way the speaker speaks, but sequentially: the speaker said something and fell silent - the translator translated - the speaker said something else and fell silent - the translator translated again, etc. Usually the speaker pauses, and the translator, accordingly, translates every 3-5 phrases.

Key words: diction, confidentiality, stress resistance, translator, information, short-term memory, source text, target text, speech.

Consecutive interpretation is used when simultaneous interpretation is not necessary or possible. Most often, this type of translation is used during bilateral negotiations, meetings, telephone conversations, installation of equipment, visiting a doctor, visiting exhibitions, court hearings, i.e. at events with a small number of participants. However, it can also be used for interpreting events with a large number of participants (conferences, seminars, presentations, receptions), if simultaneous interpretation is not required. For example, a foreign speaker speaks in English for a Russian-speaking audience, and a consecutive interpreter translates his speech into Russian for the entire audience. If translation is required into different target languages, then simultaneous translation is needed.

Skills and professional qualities of a consecutive interpreter

Knowledge of working languages. A consecutive translator must have an ideal knowledge of the languages that will be used (or rather, from which and into which he is going to translate). Be on topic. The translator must understand the topic being discussed. Incorrect translation of some specialized terms or phrases may negatively affect the results of negotiations. Even if the translator has a rich vocabulary and broad erudition, he needs to prepare for the translation. To do this, you need to request materials on the topic from the customer in advance. For example, brochures, booklets, website or other materials.

Good diction. The interpreter must speak confidently, clearly and intelligibly. Every word he says must be clear. The mutual understanding of the speakers and the success of the negotiations depend on this. It is important to speak loudly enough so that everyone can hear. Therefore, the translator must learn to use his voice. There are special exercises for this. For self-control, you can sometimes record yourself on a voice recorder and check your diction.

Purity of speech. A good translator always monitors the correctness and purity of his speech, even when he is not at work. The reason is that speech errors (incomplete sentences, filler words, obscene expressions, etc.) will certainly appear when working under stressful conditions if the translator is accustomed to them in everyday life. The translator's speech must be impeccable.

Trained memory. A consecutive interpreter must memorize part of the speaker's speech, and then present it in another language as accurately, clearly and concisely as possible. Of course, you can't do this without an excellent memory. Fortunately, memory can be trained.

Knowledge of the cultures of your language pair. People of different cultures acquire different “background knowledge” through education. Since childhood, they have been reading different books, using different metaphors and sayings, watching different films, celebrating different holidays. Therefore, it is sometimes difficult for speakers of different languages to understand each other. Therefore, the translator’s task is to study the cultures of his language pair: read books and newspapers, watch films, communicate with native speakers.

Stress resistance. Negotiations, circumstances and clients can be difficult. Therefore, a translator must be able to maintain composure in different situations and be able to quickly respond to the situation that arises. It is useful for a translator to study and master stress management and relaxation techniques (for example, meditation).

Impartiality. The translator should not express his attitude to the content of what he is translating. Also, you cannot change intonation and accents or “improve” the speaker’s speech. His task is to convey the speech as the speaker presented it. You must always remember that the translator does not participate in the dialogue, but only conveys its content. Ideally, the translator will not be visible to the participants in the conversation.

Confidentiality. The professional responsibility of the translator is to maintain the confidentiality of what he learned while attending negotiations, conversations, closed seminars, etc. Sometimes the client asks the translator to sign a written non-disclosure agreement. This is fine.

A common sense approach to translating offensive language. The translator’s task is to help the interlocutors understand each other and come to an agreement with each other if they want to. Therefore, if it is obvious that one of the speakers deliberately uses offensive expressions (for example, in order to unbalance his interlocutor), then the translator must translate them. If the speaker unintentionally uses offensive expressions (for example, he is used to using them in everyday life), then the translator can reduce their intensity or not translate at all.

Public speaking skills. This skill is very important in consecutive interpreting. A translator should not be afraid to speak in public. On the contrary, he must be fluent in verbal and non-verbal means of transmitting information.

The interpreter must sit so that he can clearly hear what the participants in the conversation are saying, and so that he can be clearly heard by those to whom he is interpreting. The translator must discuss this with the organizers or the client in advance. This is in the interests of all participants in the event. If inexperienced organizers try to seat the interpreter in an inconvenient place, for example, at the end of the table, then the interpreter should politely but persistently ask to be moved.

Which side of the client should I sit on? Usually a person hears better with one ear than the other. As a rule, right-handed people hear better with their right ear, and left-handed people hear better with their left ear. The interpreter may ask the client which side to sit on. Or don’t ask directly, but check it yourself. To do this, you need to approach the client before the conversation, stand at a distance of one and a half meters, and talk to him on an abstract topic. If the client begins to turn one side towards the interpreter, then he will probably hear better from that side.

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